

Biologically active metal complexes with phenothiazines and related ligands : a review

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The review mainly deals with the analytical, biological and structural aspects of the biologically active metal complexes with phenothiazines and related ligands. The work described primarily belongs to the author's and his associates.

The metal complexes play an important role in biological system in which enzymes are known to be activated by metal ions¹. The participation of the metalloproteins in respiratory, photosynthetic, nitrogen fixation, biosynthetic and metabolic processes is essential to the foundation of life. Several cobalt complexes are important as models to the metal-to-oxygen bonding that is involved in biological systems. Cobalt is the constituent of vitamin B₁₂. Proteins containing iron participate in oxygen transport. A number of copper proteins including enzymes have been reported². Complexes of tetrapyrrole systems, porphine or its derivatives provide a rapid planar environment for magnesium(II) ions. The most important of such derivatives are the chlorophylls and related compounds which are of transcendental importance in photosynthesis in plants.

Apart from the bioinorganic chemistry, the coordination chemistry has sustained interest in catalysis, thermodynamics, kinetics, spectral and magnetic properties of the complexes; the areas are still offering many interesting and challenging problems to be resolved. Many metal complexes of phthalocyanine, anthraquinone, azomethane and nitroso ligands find important applications in the field of photography, analysis and modern high technology industries such as electronics^{3,4}.

The chemistry of metal complexes with phenothiazine and also with heterocyclic compounds containing nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen as ligand atoms has attracted increasing attention. Phenothiazines have been reported to possess anticholinergic, antiparkinsonian, antiemetic, antispasmodic and local anaesthetic activities which are the essential requirements of antiulcer drugs. Many phenothiazines and related drugs have been reported to modulate multidrug resistance (MDR) in a number of resistance tumour cells⁵.

In view of the increasing importance of phenothiazine drugs, a detailed study of these drugs was undertaken by us.

Quality assurance and control of pharmaceutical chemi-

cals and formulations is essential for ensuring the availability of safe and effective drug formulations to consumers. Quantitative estimation of the chemical entity of a drug is vital for maintaining and assuring the quality. Several distinct problems are encountered in the quantification of the drugs in bulk samples and formulations. The interferences caused by a number of sources such as the degradation products of the drugs in combination products and the various additives incorporated in formulations have to be kept in view during the course of assay development for drug formulations. Among the various techniques, visible spectrophotometry combines the advantages of low cost and simplicity with the possibility and selectivity with good precision, accuracy and reliability.

Keeping these points in view, we have examined the present state of development of such analytical methods for some of the widely used chemotherapeutic agents. The study has been extensive in including actual samples from market and such variants as excipients a matter of great importance when one considers the practical applications. A noteworthy feature of this study is the successful effort to pin down the nature of the species in all the cases.

Spectrophotometric investigations on several phenothiazine derivatives were carried out and new procedures were developed, optimized and proposed employing silicotungstic acid⁶, molybdophosphoric acid⁷, tungstophosphoric acid⁸, molybdoarsenic acid⁹, alizarin Red-S¹⁰, chloramine-T¹¹, iodobismuthate¹², vanadophosphoric acid¹³, potassium bromate¹⁴, sodium vanadate^{15,20}, potassium iodate^{16,21}, vanadoboric acid^{17,18,24}, potassium ferricyanide¹⁹, cobalt thiocyanate^{22,23} and iodic acid²⁵. Some of the new methods for the assay of phenothiazine include polarography²⁶, conductometry²⁷, GLC²⁸, TLC²⁹ and reverse-phase HPLC³⁰.

A thorough investigations on the reactions involving some phenothiazines and metal ions such as palladium³¹⁻³⁴, ruthenium³⁵⁻³⁸, osmium³⁹⁻⁴² and gold⁴³ were carried out.

Charge transfer complexes

Pacatol forms a 1 : 1 solid charge transfer complex with picric acid involving hydrogen bonding⁴⁴.

Ion-association complexes

A large number of ion-association complexes were synthesised and characterized by conventional methods. Mixed ligand complexes of tungsten⁴⁵, cobalt⁴⁶, rhenium^{47,48}, molybdenum^{49,50}, niobium^{51,52}, zirconium⁵³⁻⁵⁵, iron⁵⁶ and cobalt⁵⁷ were isolated and attempts were made to elucidate their structures.

Biologically active metal complexes

We reported the synthesis, magnetic, spectral and thermal studies of palladium(II) complexes with potentially bidentate heterocyclic nitrogen donors⁵⁸. Structure and antimicrobial activity of some diphenylpyrrole complexes of iron(III) chloride, nitrate, sulphate and thiocyanate were reported⁵⁹. Various aspects of complexes of diphenylpyrrole with cobalt(II)⁶⁰, copper⁶¹, palladium^{62,63} were discussed. Studies on antifungal activity of iron(III), cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes showed enhanced activity⁶⁴ which may be exploited for suitable application.

Twentyfour complexes of cadmium and twentysix cobalt complexes of dothiepin (DOT), diphenhydramine (DP), doxepin (DOX) and imipramine (IP) were synthesised and characterized⁶⁵ with a view to find the coordination behavior of ligands towards metal in presence of various coordinating anions. The magnetic moment values suggest an octahedral structure for the cobalt complexes except the thiocyanato complex which exhibits tetrahedral geometry. The electronic, spectral and ligand field parameters support the above structures as also the nmr and X-ray diffraction data.

New complexes of the general formula $[Pd(IP)Cl_2]$, $[Pd(L)_2Cl_2]$, $[M(IP)H_2OC_1_3]$ and $[M(L)_2H_2OC_1_3]$ (where $M = Rh^{III}$ or Ru^{III} , $L = DOT, DP$ or DOX) were isolated and characterized⁶⁵.

A series of new complexes of cobalt(II), iron(III), copper(II), palladium(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) with different anions as primary ligands and ethopropazine (EP), fluphenazine (FP), mepazine (MP) and thioproperazine (TPP) were synthesised and their structures elucidated with the help of electronic, ir, far-ir, nmr, esr and X-ray diffraction data⁶⁶. Some studies on transition metal-phenothiazine complexes have also been reported by several workers⁶⁷⁻⁷³.

Thermal studies

Thermal degradation kinetics of cobalt(II)⁷⁴, palladium(II), rhodium(III), ruthenium(III), cadmium(II)⁷⁵ and mercury(II) complexes with various ligands have been carried out. Temperature characteristics such as T_0 , T_{10} , T_{20} and T_{max} were evaluated and the results showed that the inorganic ligands have a stronger effect on the thermal

stability of the complexes. The thermal degradation process was found to proceed in three steps for the Co^{II} , Rh^{III} and Ru^{III} complexes, whereas the Cd^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes exhibited two-step degradation. The final residue obtained in each case was identified as metal oxide.

On the basis of thermal decomposition data, various kinetic and thermodynamic parameters such as activation energy, pre-exponential factor, enthalpy, entropy and free energy were computed by employing Broido's method and standard relation. The activation energy and enthalpy increase with increasing thermal degradation steps. The entropy value is negative for first step and the free energy value is positive for all the three stages.

Biological activity

In view of the rapid development and also challenging demands, it has become necessary to isolate and screen newer compounds for antimicrobial activity. Such a study is highly useful to evaluate the possibilities of the use of metal complexes against microorganisms and to check their biodegradation in the environment. It is well known that the heterocyclic compounds exhibit bactericidal, fungicidal, herbicidal and insecticidal activities. When such heterocyclic ligands are complexed with the metal ions they exhibit enhanced microbiological activities^{76,77}.

The *in vitro* biocidal activities of the ligands DOT, DP, DOX and IP and their metal complexes were tested against two bacteria and three fungi⁶⁵ – *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Alternaria alternata*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus niger*. The antimicrobial activity of the metal complexes was found higher than that of the corresponding ligands. This may be due to extensive conjugation effects observed in the metal complexes compared to the free ligands.

Thirty new complexes of cobalt, iron, copper, palladium, platinum, cadmium and mercury with thioproperazine, ethoproperazine, fluphenazine, mepazine and pipazethate were tested for their antimicrobial effects on several strains of bacteria, yeast and moulds at different pH, temperature and concentrations in comparison with standard antibiotics^{66,78-83}. It was shown that the control of antibiotic resistant bacteria with thioproperazine with some metal complexes offers as a crop protectant.

Crystal structure of metal complexes of biological importance

The X-ray crystallographic studies on a number of complexes of biological importance were undertaken with a view to obtain greater insight into their function, activity and property. The result of such a study has thrown more light on structure-reactivity correlation in biological systems.

Crystal structure of lignocaine hydrochloride-platinum complex was solved⁸⁴ using MULTAN 80. Crystal struc-

ture of lignocaine-tetrachlorocuprate⁸⁵ was determined by X-ray crystallography. The crystal structure of diphenylpyraline hydrochloride-cobalt chloride complex⁸⁵ was solved (Fig. 1). ORTEP plot of the molecule of cobalt chloride-dothiepin hydrochloride⁸⁷ is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Projection of the molecule on the best plane.

Fig. 2. ORTEP plot of the molecules.

On our part, we have made a modest attempt to investigate the different aspects of metal complexes of phenothiazines and related ligands with biological relevance and hope to make significant contribution in the area of bioinorganic chemistry.

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